

of the region are listed in the table. Dr. N. C. Pant, director, British Museum, London; and Dr. A. D. Pawar, assistant director (Biological Control), Directorate of Plant Protection Quarantine & Storage, assisted in the identification. ■

Table continued

Natural enemy	Host	Prevalence	Years of occurrence
<i>Aphidius</i> spp.	"	High	"
<i>Selina westermanni</i> (Mots.)	"	High	"
Spiders	"	High	"
<i>Amphipsyche meridiana</i> Ulmer	"	High	1975-76

Leaffolder outbreak in Kohima District, Nagaland, India

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Rice leaffolder *Cnaphalocis medinalis* Guenee was recorded as a minor pest in 1977 and 1978. But the pest caused heavy damage during the 1979 wet season (Jun-Nov), with infestations peaking in early September. Infestation

on IR8 leaves varied from 20% at higher altitudes (1,400 m mean sea level [MSL]) to 36% at lower altitudes (250 m MSL). Infestations seem to be increasing, up to 70% on IR8 and local variety Nagaland Special in 1981. ■

Gall midge incidence at Manipur, India

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A heavy incidence of gall midge was recorded during 1979-80 kharif in a few pockets of Manipur. To assess the extent of pest incidence, a field survey was conducted in six subdivisions when the crop reached the mid- to late-tillering stage. Fifty hills per variety per loukol (a group of fields) was the survey unit. Observations were recorded from four survey units per subdivision. Varieties planted varied among subdivisions. Percentage of silver shoots was calculated on the basis of actual number of silver shoots and number of tillers per

Gall midge infestation in 6 subdivisions of Manipur, India.

Rice variety	Silver shoots (%)						Mean
	Imphal West 1	Imphal West 11	Imphal East	Thoubal	Bishenour	Churachandpur	
Punshi	22.0	12.7	32.4	23.8	15.0	—	21.2
Phouoibi	26.7	14.2	26.0	38.3	16.9	—	22.4
IR24	43.6	10.8	29.3	23.3	19.4	12.7	23.3
Ratna	46.4	—	6.9	23.2	—	24.5	25.2
P.33	42.1	9.8	—	5.6	21.0	—	19.6
Moirangphou	—	17.7	9.6	4.9	3.9	9.5	9.1
Phourel	—	—	6.2	5.1	6.5	11.27	7.2
Mean	36.2	13.0	18.4	17.8	13.8	14.7	18.3
CD (P = 0.05)	3.17	5.25	4.33	6.03	5.11	2.82	

unit.

Gall midge incidence (see table) was highest in Imphal West I and lowest in Imphal West II. The lowest use of plant protection in Imphal West I perhaps accounted for the high incidence of the pest there. In Churachandpur, gall

midge incidence was low because the area planted to susceptible high yielding varieties was small. Ratna, IR24, Punshi, and Phouoibi were found to be more susceptible to the insect than local varieties Phourel and Moirangphou (see table). ■

Occurrence of rice stem borers and gall midges at Tirur, Chingleput District, India

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To determine the damage patterns of yellow stem borer and gall midge, two major pests of rice in Chingleput, the susceptible variety IR8 was planted in 40-m² plots every month from July 1978 to June 1979. Recommended agronomic practices were adopted. The crop was given no insecticide treatment.

Stem borer and gall midge infestations were assessed at 60 days after transplanting by recording the number

Rice stem borer and gall midge damage to IR8 at Tirur, India, 1978-79.

of deadhearts and silver shoots.

The data on pests and grain yield for each planting were plotted (see figure). These conclusions were drawn:

1. Stem borer occurrence was below the economic threshold (5%) on crops planted in September and from December to June.

2. Gall midge incidence was low on crops planted from September to January and in May and June.
3. The normal times of planting in the three seasons — September in samba, January in navarai, and June in sornavari — are ideal. Crops yielded higher than average,

12.5 kg/40 m² (3.1 t/ha). Among the three seasons the highest yield was recorded in navarai.

4. In a season, early or late plantings should be accompanied by timely plant protection measures to avoid yield losses to stem borers and gall midges. ■

Minimum insecticide for rice pest control

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Monitoring pest populations on rice and adopting economic thresholds have minimized insecticide spraying in the village of Buddam, Andhra Pradesh.

The average number of sprays before starting an ICORP project was 2.1 sprays in the wet season and 2.7 sprays in the dry season. But when sprays were made only when needed, the average number was reduced to as low as zero sprays in the 1977-78 wet season. Spraying was done only once on 9.72 ha and in the remaining 395 ha a good crop was raised without spraying at all. In general, economic loss due to insect pests was avoided during the period of the project (Table 1). And fewer sprays were made without loss in yield.

Field sample plots provide data to initiate control operations. Plots 0.4 ha in size and representative of varieties and dates of planting are selected, and 5 m² in each provides the area for counting deadhearts at 15, 30, 55 days after transplanting (DT) and silver shoots at

15 and 35 DT. Counts on 50 hills at random provide the data for other pests.

When the pest density or damage is above an economic threshold (Table 2) in a large number of sample plots, a general survey of farmers' fields is undertaken. Insecticide is applied in fields where an economic threshold has been exceeded.

Other benefits also have been noticed. Incidence of pests in general was low, and the onset of incidence was delayed compared to surrounding areas. Predators of brown planthopper and parasites of gall midge and stem borer contributed increasingly to natural control.

In implementing integrated control, economic thresholds were modified in three cases:

1. In the dry season, stem borer attack develops within 15-20 DT. As the crop at this stage has very few tillers, stem borer attack can result in seedling death and gaps in the field. It is desirable to spray insecticide when the damage reaches 5% deadhearts. Deadheart counts must be taken 15, 30, and 55 DT.
2. Brown planthopper large-scale egg laying occurs during favorable climatic conditions in the preflowering and postflowering stages. Nymph density instead of adult

Table 2. Tentative economic thresholds for pest control. Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests, Bapatla, India.

Pest	Threshold
Stem borers	10% deadhearts
Gall midge	5% silvershoots
Green leafhopper) Brown leafhopper)	25 insects/hill
Leaffolder	3 damaged leaves/hill
Cutworms) Rice hispa) Grasshoppers)	1 insect/hill

density provides a better basis for control operations. The presence of 25 nymphs/hill was found to be a useful economic threshold.

3. Since it is difficult to locate the climbing cutworm caterpillars, a better indicator than density is cut panicles. The presence of 5 cut panicles/m² should be the threshold for insecticidal spraying. ■

Effect of volume of insecticide spray on brown planthopper mortality

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Reducing the volume of water in insecticide spray minimizes the cost of farm labor to carry water to the area of application. To determine whether insecticide toxicity is affected by spray volumes, 250, 500, and 1,000 liters insecticide solutions/ha were sprayed on 30- to 35-day-old TN1 potted plants at a rate of 0.75 kg ai/ha using an atomizer run by an air compressor. Beginning one day after treatment (DAT) 20 female adult brown planthoppers were caged on treated plants at 5-day intervals. Insect mortality was recorded 48 hours after caging.

Table 1. Effect of insecticide sprays on rice yield in Bapatla, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Year	Wet season				Dry season			
	ICORP village		Control village		ICORP village		Control village	
	Sprays (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Sprays (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Sprays (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Sprays (no.)	Yield (t/ha)
1974-75 ^a	2.1	4.23	2.8	3.57	2.7	3.15	3.2	3.33
1975-76	1.4	3.75	2.1	2.53	0.7	4.50	3.1	4.40
1976-77	0.3	5.00	0.2	3.33	0.3	4.18	2.3	4.19
1977-78	0.0	4.60 ^b 1.77 ^c	0.2	2.65	1.5	3.52	1.6	3.18
1978-79	0.1	4.01	0.4	3.65	—	—	—	—
1979-80	0.3	4.20	0.5	4.00	—	—	—	—

^aBase year. ^bYield before a cyclone. ^cYield after a cyclone.